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Questionnaire on Indicators of Incorporation and Use of Educational Technologies in Moroccan Public Universities

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1. Introduction

The project "Support to the Higher Education system in Morocco within the framework of a rapprochement with the European Higher Education Area" (*Appui au Système de l'Enseignement supérieur au Maroc dans le cadre d'un rapprochement avec l'Espace européen de l'Enseignement*), is an European Project whose general objective is accompanying, assisting and promoting the reform of the Moroccan higher education system within the framework of its strategic vision 2015-2030 and its approach to the European Higher Education Area in order to improve the employability of graduates and the governance of the university system. The project is organized into 6 components that involve different Spanish institutions.

In the development of component 3 (Mission 3.1), *Diversification des modalités d'enseignement (stratégie eLearning)*, it is important to have a basic knowledge of some indicators on the incorporation and use of educational technologies in Moroccan Public Universities. To this end, we present in the framework of this project a simple questionnaire, which each public university must answer separately. In this sense, it is important that the answers reflect the reality of each institution in the most reliable way possible. The data collected aimed to facilitate, on the one hand, the making of recommendations by the panel of experts of this Component 3. On the other hand, the information collected aims to guide the decision making in the use of educational technologies and in the definition of an eLearning strategy (García-Peñalvo & Seoane-Pardo, 2015; Gros & García-Peñalvo, 2016) in the Moroccan Public University System, both at the ministerial level and individually by the heads of the Moroccan Public Universities.

The UNIVERSITIC reports (CRUE TIC, 2014; Gómez, 2016, 2018; Píriz, 2015), made by CRUE Universidades Españolas, have been taken as reference for the realization of this questionnaire <http://www.crue.org/SitePages/Universitic.aspx>.

2. Questionnaire

2.1. General information

Q001. University name.

Q002. Location of the university's headquarters.

Q003. Number of campus.

Q004. Number of students (Less than 10,000; 10,001 – 25,000; 25,001 – 50,000; 50,001 – 75,000; 75,001 – 100,000; More than 100,000)

Q005. Number of teachers.

Q006. Number of administrative staff.

2.2. Support and infrastructure

Q007. ICT support services provided to teachers

- **Q007_1.** Virtual teaching
- **Q007_2.** Support to the teaching computer rooms
- **Q007_3.** Management of software licenses for teaching
- **Q007_4.** Support to the open-access computer rooms
- **Q007_5.** Support to the multimedia classrooms
- **Q007_6.** Support to the development of teaching contents
- **Q007_7.** Support to completion and correction of exams

Q008. Number of ICT support services provided to teachers from the cloud.

Q009. Number of ICT support services provided to teachers using free software.

Q010. Percentage of WiFi network coverage in the spaces of the University:

Q011. Is the WiFi network available to all students of the university? (Yes / No)

Q012. Is the WiFi network available to all teachers of the university? (Yes/ No)

Q013. Is the WiFi network available for guests? (Yes / No)

Q014. Connection speed to the network *Moroccan Academic and Research Wide Area Network* (MARWAN) (Less than 50MB; 50MB – 100MB; 100MB – 1GB; 1GB – 5GB; 5GB – 10GB; More than 10GB)

Q015. The University has its own infrastructure for virtual services (own servers or cloud) (Yes / No)

Q016. Number of classrooms with basic computer equipment (all student seats connected to the internet and multimedia projector).

Q017. Number of open-access computers.

2.3. Virtual teaching support

Q018. Good practices related to virtual teaching (select all the options that apply):

- **Q018_1.** Recording rooms
- **Q018_2.** Web portal
- **Q018_3.** Mobile devices
- **Q018_4.** Standards for content creation
- **Q018_5.** Virtual teaching Inter-University Networks
- **Q018_6.** Virtual rights: intellectual property control
- **Q018_7.** Flipped Classroom practices
- **Q018_8.** SPOC (Small Private Online Course)

Q019. Is there a unique official virtual teaching platform at the University? (Yes / No)

Q020. If yes, which?

Q021. Number of teachers using the virtual platform.

Q022. Does the University manage its own platform for the development of MOOC / SPOC?

Q023. If yes, which?

Q024. Number of MOOCs offered by the University.

Q025. Does the University have an official streaming support system? (Yes / No)

Q026. If yes, which?

Q027. Does the University have an official videoconferencing system? (Yes / No)

Q028. If yes, which?

2.4. Information management

Q029. Does the University have an institutional digital repository? (Yes / No)

Q030. Is there an institutional policy on open access to digital content? (Yes / No)

Q031. Is there interoperability between the institutional digital repository and the virtual platform? (Yes / No)

2.4. Training

Q032. Does the university provide IT training courses to the teaching staff? (Yes / No)

Q033. Does the university provide IT training courses to the administrative staff? (Yes / No)

Q034. Does the university provide IT training courses to the students? (Yes / No)

Q035. Indicate the main topics on which the University offers IT training courses.

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